
CyberContingency Planning: Business Impact Analysis & Business Interruption Risk

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Abstract

Every day, more and more companies are becoming at risk of being shut down due to various causes. Weather disasters, fires, physical theft, the human factor, are only the tip of the iceberg when it comes to a company's risk management planning. Cyber-hacking, online identity theft and database warehouse attacks are risks that are becoming more and more real as technology progresses. This paper will address and discuss multiple possible risks that can cause business interruption. This paper will also discuss how to prevent these risks and prepare for them in the case that they do happen. It will also explain how to create a cybercontingency plan, who is responsible for developing the plan, implementing it, and who can access the plan within the company. A sample cybercontingency plan is provided in Part 5 of this paper as a hypothetical example of a made-up company to illustrate the real-life language of a cybercontingency plan.

Keywords: cybercontingency, technology risks, cybersecurity
